

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15443037

Potential of Horse Solid Waste (HSW) Pyrolysis for Organic Biochar Production as a Solid Enrichment Manure in Birnin Kebbi Soil

Danshehu Bagudu Gwadangaji ^{1*}, Bemgba Bevan Nyakuma ², Abdullahi Tanko Mohammed ^{3*}
Farooq Abubakar Atiku⁴ Abba Muhammad Adua⁵

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering,
Faculty of Engineering,
Kebbi State University of Science and Technology, Aliero, Kebbi State, Nigeria.

²Department of Chemical Sciences,
Faculty of Science and Computing,
North-Eastern University, Gombe, Gombe State, Nigeria

³ Department of Mechanical Engineering,
Waziri Umaru Federal Polytechnic, Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State, Nigeria

⁴Department of Pure and Industrial Chemistry,
Kebbi State University of Science and Technology, Aleiro, Kebbi State, Nigeria

⁵Department of Electrical/Electronics Engineering,
Kebbi State University of Science and Technology, Aleiro, Kebbi State, Nigeria

*Corresponding author(s) email: bg.danshehu@ksusta.ed.ng, tankoacada1@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In this study, comparative pyrolysis of horse manure (HM) and cattle dung (CD) using a drum kiln pyrolyser for the production of organic biochar manure for soil enrichment application was conducted. The process was carried out at 600 °C and residence time of 60 minutes, during which the dark brown HM and CD samples were successfully converted into carbon-black rich biochar materials. The biochar was subsequently characterised through analysis of the potential hydrogen (pH), electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solids (TDS), oxidation-reduction potential (ORP), and salinity (SAL). The results showed dark and clear colourations from the HM and CD biochar filtrates, respectively, suggesting that HM contains high contents of dissolved organic materials (such as humic acids, tannins and other bio-nutrients) compared to CD. The physicochemical analysis revealed significant differences in the HM and CD biochars. The HM exhibited potentials for higher nutrient availability, alkalinity, and ionic presence, whereas CD offers superior stability and electrical conductivity. In addition, the results show that HM

biochar can enhance pH stabilization and nutrient mobility, whereas CD balances the soil environment, reducing the risk of extreme salt accumulation. Overall, the results show that HM and CD are potentially viable raw materials for organic biochar manure production.

Keywords: Pyrolysis, Horse Manure, Cattle Dung, Biochar Production, Soil Enrichment, Waste Valorisation.

1. INTRODUCTION

The era of sustainable agriculture has heightened interest in soil management practices [1], particularly the use of organic amendments that enhance soil fertility and mitigate environmental degradation [2]. Amongst these promising approaches is the application of biochar [3], which is a carbon-rich substance synthesised from the process of biomass pyrolysis [4]. Biochar has attracted significant interest over the years due to its potential to enhance the health of soils, retain nutrients, and the activity of microbes [5, 6]. In addition, biochar has exceptional physical and chemical properties suitable for conditioning soils, stabilising organic matter, and reducing greenhouse gas emissions [7].

Despite its extensive recognition globally, the process of selecting appropriate raw materials or feedstocks for biochar production remains a challenge [8]. Biochar material selection is a crucial factor that impacts the quality, efficiency, and yield of biochar and its applications [9]. The wastes from animal husbandry, such as manures, present a valuable yet underutilised alternative resource for the production of biochar [10]. These opportunities stem from the rich composition and availability of nutrients in the manures from various animals [11]. However, the differences in manure types and pyrolysis performance during conversion into biochar present operational challenges.

Hence, there is a need for comprehensive studies to identify and examine the optimal raw material/feedstock for sustainable biochar production and soil enhancement. The breeding of horses and cattle across the globe generates large quantities of solid wastes termed horse manure (HM) and cattle dung (CD), respectively. The manures HM and CD are solid wastes comprising different organic and inorganic constituents that impact their suitability for conversion into biochar [12]. HM consists of fibrous materials that could enhance the structural integrity and stability of biochar, whereas CD has high moisture content and microbial variety [13]. Previously, researchers have examined biochar synthesis from various organic feedstocks [14].

However, there are currently no comparative studies on the valorisation of HM and CD into biochar. Likewise, comparative studies of manure-derived biochars, especially from HM and CD, remain scarce. Current studies have explored single manure sources with comparison of the pyrolytic performance, physicochemical characteristics, and soil enhancement potentials of HM and CD biochar manure. Furthermore, studies on the impact of biochar manure on major soil physicochemical properties such as pH stabilization, electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solids (TDS), oxidation-reduction potential (ORP), and salinity (SAL) remain insufficiently explored in the literature. The outlined research gaps are currently hampering efforts to effectively design biochar formulations for specific soil situations and agricultural purposes. Therefore, this study seeks to comparatively investigate the pyrolysis of HM and CD into organic biochar manure and examine the potential impact of the biochars as soil enhancement materials.

2. MATERIALS & METHODS

2.1 Materials

The horse manure (HM) examined in this study was obtained from the horse stables at the Emir of Gwandu's Palace, Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State, Nigeria. The town is located on latitude 12°28'11" N, longitude 4°13'57" E in the Sudan-Savannah agro-ecological zone of North-western part of Nigeria [15]. The HM samples were collected in sterile polyethylene sample bags, labelled, and transported for further analysis. Next, the HM was air and sun-dried for 3 weeks before pyrolysis. On the other hand, the cattle dung (CD) was acquired from the Kara Cattle Market in Birnin Kebbi town, Kebbi State. The CD samples were subsequently bagged and transported for further analysis. The samples were then dried for 3 weeks

before pyrolysis was performed. **Figure 5** shows the raw HM and CD animal wastes acquired for analysis in this study.

Figure 5: Animal waste materials for pyrolysis (a) Horse Manure (b) Cattle Dung

As observed, the HM occurs as a solid compact and dark brown to black mass of material that is coarse, fibrous, and visible strands, which may be ascribed to the presence of poorly digested plant materials. Conversely, the CD is a solid and dense mass of dark brown colour with a uniform and less fibrous texture, which suggests finer consistency and smoother surface compared to HM.

2.2 METHODS

2.2.1 Pyrolysis process

The objective of the study was to conduct comparative pyrolysis of HM and CD for organic biochar manure production as soil enrichment materials. Hence, the drum kiln pyrolyser (DKP) shown in

Figure 2 was designed and constructed for this purpose. For each test, about 30 kg of the HM and CD samples were loaded into the DKP and pyrolysed for 60 60-minute residence time, while the pyrolysis temperature of the process was monitored using a non-contact infrared temperature measuring thermometer device. The average temperature of the pyrolysis process of the materials was ~600 °C. On

Figure 6: Drum kiln pyrolyser for HM and CD pyrolysis

2.2.2 Parametric Biochar /Physicochemical Characterisation

After cooling for 3 hours, the HM and CD biochar samples were subjected to parametric characterisation to ascertain their suitability for application as enrichment materials for soils. The characterisation tests performed were: potential hydrogen (pH), electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solids (TDS), oxidation-reduction potential (ORP), and salinity (SAL). To test each parameter, each biochar sample was ground into a powder form using a dry milling machine (Model: Royal Silver Crest, China). The fine powdered materials were subsequently weighed using a weighing balance (Model: ElectroCompact Scale SF-400D, China) to obtain 5 g of each.

Next, the weighed mass of each biochar material was placed in a 500 ml beaker (Adarsh Borosilicate Glass), before adding 100 ml of distilled water based on the ratio of 20:1 (g/v), according to the procedure described in the literature [16]. The mixture was agitated in a magnetic stirrer (Model: JOANLAB Magnetic Stirrer, China) and stirrer bar (2 cm) for 5 minutes and then filtered using a filtration set-up comprising funnel-retort stand-filter paper (Smith Filter Paper 101, 125 mm). The filtrate was then tested for the pH, EC, TDS, ORP, and SAL using the multiparameter meter (Model: Water Quality Tester, Multifunctional Analysis Instrument, China). Each test was performed in triplicate, and the average of each was presented in the results section.

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

3.1 Biochar Form, Morphology and Structural Characteristics

The pyrolysis experiments in the DKP produced a solid mass of HM and CD biochar materials as shown in **Figure 3**. The results indicate that the raw waste materials were fully converted from their initial dark brown into black coloured materials typically observed in pyrolysed materials. The black coloured mass observed for the biochar samples also indicates the formation of high-carbon materials [17].

Figure 7: Biochar manure from (a) horse manure; (b) cattle dung

Further analysis shows that HM biochar retains the rough, fibrous texture of the raw material, although it now has more visible cracks and an uneven surface. The observed structural changes could be ascribed to the thermochemical transformations that occurred during the pyrolysis process [18], which enriched the materials with more stable carbon compounds evident in the black colour of the product. Despite its solid structure, the HM biochar exhibits a degree of brittleness due to the impact of the pyrolysis treatment process [19]. On the other hand, the CD biochar revealed a more porous structure, which indicates substantial modification of its composition when compared to the raw material. Further analysis shows that the CD biochar has a rough and crumbly texture (unlike the raw material), characterised by small cracks distributed along its surface. This observation suggests that CD biochar is highly porous and lightweight in nature.

3.2 Biochar Manure Filtrate Analysis

The filtrate of each biochar obtained from the filtration process (as shown in **Figure 4**) was used to examine its potential characteristics for soil enhancement. The colours of HM and CD biochar filtrates were first examined to elucidate any insights into their constituents and prospective impacts on the enhancement of soils. As observed, the colours of the biochar filtrates have distinct appearances, which emphasise major chemical features that could potentially impact the health and fertility of soils.

Figure 8: Filtrate from (a) horse manure; (b) cow dung biochar

Figure 4(a) shows that the HM biochar filtrate is characterised by a deep brown colouration, which suggests the presence of a high content of dissolved organic materials [20]. The dark colouration could also be due to the presence of humic substances, tannins and bio-nutrients [21] in the HM biochar, which

could potentially enhance the health and fertility of soils. Studies have reported that such materials have the potential to retain moisture, soil structure, and increase soil microbes, which promote the proper growth and development of soils [22].

Conversely, the CD biochar filtrate showed a clear colouration, which could suggest that it contains a lower content of organic dissolved compounds. The results could also indicate that the crucial minerals and nutrients in the biochar are efficiently preserved but not leached, as could also occur when applied in the soils. Consequently, the CD biochar has the potential to support extended stabilisation of nutrients, enhance aeration, and balance moisture without excessive runoff of nutrients in soils [23].

3.3 Physicochemical Characteristics of Biochar

The physicochemical characteristics of HM and CD, namely, EC, TDS, ORP, and SAL, were examined using the filtrate of the biochar manures. **Table 1** presents the potential hydrogen (pH), electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solids (TDS), oxidation-reduction potential (ORP), and salinity (SAL) properties of the HM and CD biochar samples examined in this study. These could be described as the physicochemical properties of the biochar samples.

Table 2: Biochar filtrate physicochemical properties of HM and CD

Property	Abbreviation (unit)	Horse Manure (HM)	Cattle Dung (CD)
Potential hydrogen	pH	10.44	9.87
Total dissolved solids	TDS	1090.27	433.71
Oxidation-reduction potential	ORP	50.33	35.00
Salinity	SAL	885.67	345.67
Electrical conductivity	EC	1787.33	711.00

The pH describes the biochar chemical properties that could impact the acidity or basicity of soils [24]. The EC defines the strength and conductivity of ions present in the biochar that could influence the accessibility to nutrients [25]. The TDS describes the composition of dissolved solids that could participate in the enrichment of soils [26]. ORP defines the redox settings that could impact the activity of microbes and the cycling of nutrients [27]. Lastly, the SAL denotes the existence of soluble salts that could impact plant health and the structure of the soils [28].

The results show that both biochar materials exhibit contrasting physicochemical characteristics. As observed, HM shows consistently higher amounts of all the investigated parameters (namely pH, TDS, EC, ORP and SAL) when compared to the CD. The higher pH value of HM (10.44) suggests that it is more alkaline than the CD (9.87), which indicates that HM will better enhance soil pH stabilisation when applied as an amendment. Similarly, the TDS and SAL of HM are significantly higher than those of CD, which suggests that HM has higher dissolved solids and salts than CD. This observation could favour the availability of nutrients but may need cautious application to prevent extreme accumulation of salts in the soils. Furthermore, the results show that HM has higher ORP values, which could adversely impact the redox settings, nutrient cycling, and microbial activity in soils when compared to CD. In addition, HM showed a significantly higher value of EC (i.e., ~2.51 times) when compared to CD, which indicates greater ionic presence, which could be beneficial to plant nutrient uptake and mobility. In general, the results showed marked variations in the properties of both HM and CD biochars. Even though HM has higher alkalinity and nutrient availability, CD offers long-term stability, as well as lower electrical conductivity (EC) and salinity (SAL) levels.

4. CONCLUSION

The study examined the comparative pyrolysis of HM and CD, the production of organic biochar manure for application as soil enrichment material. The dark brown coloured HM and CD raw materials were successfully pyrolysed in a drum kiln pyrolyser into black carbon-rich mass of biochar materials with additionally modified textures and surfaces. Biochar filtrate analysis revealed the presence of dark and

clear hues for HM and CD, which suggests that the former contains a higher content of dissolved organic materials such as humic acids, tannins and other bio-nutrients compared to the latter. The physicochemical analysis revealed prominent distinctions in the physicochemical characteristics of HM and CD biochars. While HM exhibited higher nutrient availability, alkalinity, and ionic presence, CD presents superior stability in the long-term and lower salinity (SAL) and electrical conductivity (EC). The observed variations in the biochar properties suggest that HM will improve stabilisation pH and nutrient mobility, while CD will balance the soil environment with a lower probability of extreme salt accumulation in soils.

REFERENCES

1. Tuğrul, K.M., *Soil management in sustainable agriculture*. Sustainable crop production, 2019.
2. Ayteneu, M. and G. Bore, *Effects of organic amendments on soil fertility and environmental quality: A review*. Plant Sci, 2020. **8**(5): p. 112-119.
3. Agarwal, H., et al., *Biochar-based fertilizers and their applications in plant growth promotion and protection*. 3 Biotech, 2022. **12**(6): p. 136.
4. Zhang, B., Y. Jiang, and R. Balasubramanian, *Synthesis, formation mechanisms and applications of biomass-derived carbonaceous materials: a critical review*. Journal of Materials Chemistry A, 2021. **9**(44): p. 24759-24802.
5. Gabhane, J.W., et al., *Recent trends in biochar production methods and its application as a soil health conditioner: a review*. SN Applied Sciences, 2020. **2**: p. 1-21.
6. Hossain, M.Z., et al., *Biochar and its importance on nutrient dynamics in soil and plant*. Biochar, 2020. **2**: p. 379-420.
7. Abhishek, K., et al., *Biochar application for greenhouse gas mitigation, contaminants immobilization and soil fertility enhancement: A state-of-the-art review*. Science of The Total Environment, 2022. **853**: p. 158562.
8. Danesh, P., et al., *Biochar production: Recent developments, applications, and challenges*. Fuel, 2023. **337**: p. 126889.
9. Panwar, N., A. Pawar, and B. Salvi, *Comprehensive review on production and utilization of biochar*. SN Applied Sciences, 2019. **1**: p. 1-19.
10. Raza, S.T., et al., *Reuse of agricultural wastes, manure, and biochar as an organic amendment: A review on its implications for vermicomposting technology*. Journal of Cleaner Production, 2022. **360**: p. 132200.
11. Prado, J., et al., *A step towards the production of manure-based fertilizers: Disclosing the effects of animal species and slurry treatment on their nutrients content and availability*. Journal of Cleaner Production, 2022. **337**: p. 130369.
12. Rehrach, D., et al., *Physico-chemical characterization of biochars from solid municipal waste for use in soil amendment*. Journal of analytical and applied pyrolysis, 2016. **118**: p. 42-53.
13. Nagel, K., et al., *Physicochemical characteristics of biochars derived from corn, hardwood, miscanthus, and horse manure biomasses*. Communications in Soil Science and Plant Analysis, 2019. **50**(8): p. 987-1002.
14. Vijayaraghavan, K., *Recent advancements in biochar preparation, feedstocks, modification, characterization and future applications*. Environmental Technology Reviews, 2019. **8**(1): p. 47-64.
15. Abdullahi, T.M., Mohammed Nazri, M.J., Othman N., Veza, I., Mohammed, B., Fatogun, A.O., and Sanda, Y.H., *Soil fertility enrichment potential of jatropha curcas for sustainable agricultural production: A case study of Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria*. Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology, 2021. 21061-21073.
16. Nyakuma, B.B., et al., *Torrefaction of oil palm empty fruit bunch pellets: Product yield, distribution and fuel characterisation for enhanced energy recovery*. Biomass Conversion and Biorefinery, 2023. **13**: p. 755-775.
17. Nyakuma, B.B., et al., *Carbon dioxide torrefaction of oil palm empty fruit bunches pellets: characterisation and optimisation by response surface methodology*. Biomass Conversion and Biorefinery, 2022. **12**: p. 5881-5900.

18. Nyakuma, B.B., S. Wong, and O. Oladokun, *Non-oxidative thermal decomposition of oil palm empty fruit bunch pellets: fuel characterisation, thermogravimetric, kinetic, and thermodynamic analyses*. Biomass Conversion and Biorefinery, 2021. **11**: p. 1273-1292.
19. Shanmugam, V., et al., *A review on combustion and mechanical behaviour of pyrolysis biochar*. Materials Today Communications, 2022. **31**: p. 103629.
20. Iqbal, H., M. Garcia-Perez, and M. Flury, *Effect of biochar on leaching of organic carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorus from compost in bioretention systems*. Science of the Total Environment, 2015. **521**: p. 37-45.
21. Ozer, H., et al., *Circular Utilization of Coffee Grounds as a Bio-Nutrient through Microbial Transformation for Leafy Vegetables*. Life, 2024. **14**(10): p. 1299.
22. Ding, Y., et al., *Biochar to improve soil fertility. A review*. Agronomy for sustainable development, 2016. **36**: p. 1-18.
23. Sharma, P., *Biochar application for sustainable soil erosion control: a review of current research and future perspectives*. Frontiers in Environmental Science, 2024. **12**: p. 1373287.
24. Chintala, R., et al., *Effect of biochar on chemical properties of acidic soil*. Archives of Agronomy and Soil Science, 2014. **60**(3): p. 393-404.
25. Singh, B., et al., *Biochar pH, electrical conductivity and liming potential*. Biochar: A guide to analytical methods, 2017. **23**.
26. Kelly, C.N., et al., *Biochar application to hardrock mine tailings: soil quality, microbial activity, and toxic element sorption*. Applied Geochemistry, 2014. **43**: p. 35-48.
27. Xiong, X., Y. Li, and C. Zhang, *Enhanced phosphorus removal from anoxic water using oxygen-carrying iron-rich biochar: Combined roles of adsorption and keystone taxa*. Water Research, 2024. **266**: p. 122433.
28. Dahlawi, S., et al., *Biochar application for the remediation of salt-affected soils: Challenges and opportunities*. Science of the Total Environment, 2018. **625**: p. 320-335.